

HOMOGENIZATION AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS FOR OPTIMAL THERMOELASTIC DESIGN OF METAL-CERAMIC COMPOSITES

Y. Sinchuk^{1*}, R. Piat¹

¹ Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany

* Corresponding author (yuriy.sinchuk@kit.edu)

Keywords: *thermoelastic optimization, sensitivity analysis, metal-ceramic composites*

1 Introduction

The purpose of this investigation is solution of thermoelastic topology optimization problem for orthotropic materials (e.g. metal-ceramics composites, MCC [1]). The goal of the optimization is to find the optimal material (lamella) orientation that results in minimal compliance energy. Optimization for pure elastic microstructure behavior is described in works [2-6]. In this paper we consider two kinds of thermoelastic models: the model with constant temperature over the specimen region and the model with temperature distribution obtained from the solution of heat conductivity problem (coupled problem). Solution of the optimization problem where the temperature field is independent of the material orientation is presented in [7, 8].

In the present work the problem is solved using the stress-based method (principal stress direction method) [3, 4]. The mathematical foundation of the methodology for finding optimal orientation of orthotropic materials is discussed in [5]. The application of the stress-based method for topology optimization of the metal-ceramic composites (MCC) specimen subjected to mechanical loads only is presented in [6]. Current study demonstrates the application of the stress-based methodology [5, 6] for coupled problem combining heat conduction and elastic loads. This paper is organized as follows: thermoelastic homogenization procedure for orthotropic MCC is given in Sect. 2; the optimization problem is described in Sect. 3; Sect. 4 and Sect. 5 present sensitivity analysis for two kinds of models (problem with constant temperature and coupled problem); in Sect. 6 the results of numerical calculations are discussed. Finally, some concluding remarks are presented.

2 Material properties

The material under consideration is MMC composite produced by freeze-casing. It has lamellar micro-

structure (see Fig.1) with alumina (Al₂O₃) and aluminum-silicon (Al₁₂Si) phases [1]. We assume that the material is orthotropic (in the freeze casting direction we have no changes of the material microstructure). The asymptotic homogenization scheme for layered materials [3] is used to calculate the effective stiffness matrix of the composite:

$$\mathbf{C}_H = \mathbf{C}_H(E_m, E_c, \nu_m, \nu_c, V_c),$$

where E_i, V_i, ν_i are Young's modulus, volume fraction and Poisson's ratio of the metal ($i = m$) and ceramic ($i = c$) phases. In two-dimensional case the stiffness matrix has the form

$$C_H = [\mathbf{C}_H] = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & 0 \\ c_{12} & c_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_{66} \end{bmatrix},$$

and the corresponding compliance matrix is found as

$$S_H = C_H^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} s_{11} & s_{12} & 0 \\ s_{12} & s_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & s_{66} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The overall thermal expansion coefficients along lamella orientation α_1 and transverse to the lamella orientation α_2 are calculated using Schapery model [9]:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 &= \frac{E_m \alpha_m V_m + E_c \alpha_c V_c}{E_m V_m + E_c V_c}, \\ \alpha_2 &= (1 + \nu_m) \alpha_m V_m + (1 + \nu_c) \alpha_c V_c - \\ &\quad - \alpha_1 (\nu_m V_m + \nu_c V_c), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where α_c and α_m are thermal expansion coefficients of the metal and ceramic phases. Examples of successful application of the model to several types of laminated ceramic composites can be found in [10].

The overall thermal conductivity of the material is calculated utilizing Voigt-Reuss approximation [11]. The effective conductivities in the directions parallel

and perpendicular to the lamella orientation are given as

$$\begin{aligned} k_1 &= V_c k_c + V_m k_m, \\ k_2 &= [V_c k_c^{-1} + V_m k_m^{-1}]^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here, thermal conductivities of ceramic and metal phases are k_c and k_m respectively.

3 Optimization problem

Consider a MMC sample that occupies domain Ω with boundary Γ subjected to tractions \mathbf{t} and temperature differential $\Delta T(\mathbf{x})$, $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega$. We want to find the optimal (in terms of compliance) distribution of material orientation $\theta = \theta(\mathbf{x})$. The constitutive law for plane-stress model of linear thermoelasticity is

$$\sigma = C(\theta)\varepsilon - \sigma_t(\theta), \quad (3)$$

where stiffness matrix is expressed as

$$C(\theta) = R^{-1}(\theta)C_H R^{-T}(\theta),$$

and thermal stress

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_t &= R^{-1}(\theta)\sigma_H, \\ \sigma_H &= \Delta T C_H \alpha = [\sigma_t^I, \sigma_t^{II}, 0]^T, \\ \alpha &= [\alpha_1, \alpha_1, 0]^T, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$R(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \theta & \sin^2 \theta & 2 \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ \sin^2 \theta & \cos^2 \theta & -2 \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ -\sin \theta \cos \theta & \sin \theta \cos \theta & \cos^2 \theta - \sin^2 \theta \end{bmatrix}$$

is the rotation matrix relating global to the material coordinate system (see Fig. 2).

The equilibrium equation in terms of unknown displacement u is

$$\int_{\Omega} [\varepsilon^T(u) C \varepsilon(v) - \sigma_t^T \varepsilon(v)] d\Omega - \int_{\Gamma} t^T v d\Gamma = 0, \quad (4)$$

from which the system of linear equations $Ku = f$ is found, where $K = K(\theta)$ is the global stiffness matrix and $f = f(\theta)$ is the load vector. The components of the vector $\theta = \theta(\mathbf{x})$ define the material orientation for each element (fixed within the element).

The design optimization problem is formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\theta} c(\theta) &= f^T(\theta) \cdot u(\theta) \\ \text{s.t.} : K(\theta)u &= f(\theta). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The nodal temperature vector T is found from the solution of heat conductivity finite element problem $K_T T = F_T$, where K_T is the global conductivity matrix, and F_T is thermal load vector. The nodal temperature change is $\Delta T = T - T_0$ for known initial temperature T_0 .

4 Sensitivity analysis (constant ΔT)

Consider sensitivity analysis for a certain element with material orientation θ . Taking into account

$$K \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\partial K}{\partial \theta} u,$$

we have the necessary optimality condition

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial c}{\partial \theta} &= \frac{\partial f^T}{\partial \theta} \cdot u + u^T K \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} = \\ &= 2 \frac{\partial f^T}{\partial \theta} \cdot u - u^T \frac{\partial K}{\partial \theta} u = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Assuming that the strain is constant within the element, the equation (6) can be reformulated in the form [7]

$$2 \frac{\partial \sigma_t^T}{\partial \theta} \varepsilon - \varepsilon^T \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta} \varepsilon = 0. \quad (7)$$

Taking into account $\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta} = -C \frac{\partial S}{\partial \theta} C$, we have

$$2 \frac{\partial \sigma_t^T}{\partial \theta} S \bar{\sigma} + \bar{\sigma}^T \frac{\partial S}{\partial \theta} \bar{\sigma} = 0, \quad (8)$$

where $\bar{\sigma} = \sigma + \sigma_t = [\bar{\sigma}_1, \bar{\sigma}_2, \bar{\sigma}_{12}]^T$.

Introducing matrix $W = \frac{\partial R^{-T}}{\partial \theta} R^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -2 & 2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ the

equation (8) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} &2 \frac{\partial [R^{-1}(\theta)\sigma_H]^T}{\partial \theta} R^T(\theta) S_H R(\theta) \bar{\sigma} + \\ &+ \bar{\sigma}^T \frac{\partial [R^T(\theta)S_H R(\theta)]}{\partial \theta} \bar{\sigma} = \\ &= 2 \bar{\sigma}_H^T W S_H R(\theta) \bar{\sigma} + \bar{\sigma}^T \frac{\partial [R^T(\theta)S_H R(\theta)]}{\partial \theta} \bar{\sigma} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Let $\sigma_{pr} = R(\gamma)\bar{\sigma} = [\sigma_1, \sigma_2, 0]^T$ for principal element stress, where γ is the angle between the first axis of the global coordinate system and the main principal stress direction of the $\bar{\sigma}$, and

$\psi = \theta - \gamma$ is the angle between the direction and the material coordinate axes (see Fig. 2). In expression (9) the differentiation with respect to θ is the same as differentiation with respect to ψ (see [7]). Assuming that the angle γ is independent of the material orientation we can transform (9) into the following

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2\bar{\sigma}_H^T W S_H R(\theta) R(-\gamma) R(\gamma) \bar{\sigma} + \bar{\sigma}^T R(\gamma)^T \times \\
& \times \frac{\partial [R^T(-\gamma) R^T(\theta) S_H R(\theta) R(-\gamma)]}{\partial \theta} R(\gamma) \bar{\sigma} = \\
& = 2\bar{\sigma}_H^T W S_H R(\psi) \sigma_{pr} + \\
& + \sigma_{pr}^T \frac{\partial [R^T(\psi) S_H R(\psi)]}{\partial \psi} \sigma_{pr} = s_{66}(\sigma_i^I - \sigma_i^{II}) \times \\
& \times [-\sin 2\psi, \sin 2\psi, 2 \cos 2\psi] \sigma_{pr} + \\
& + \sigma_{pr}^T \frac{\partial [R^T(\psi) S_H R(\psi)]}{\partial \psi} \sigma_{pr} = \\
& = s_{66}(\sigma_i^I - \sigma_i^{II}) \sin 2\psi (\sigma_2 - \sigma_1) + \\
& + \sigma_{pr}^T \frac{\partial [R^T(\psi) S_H R(\psi)]}{\partial \psi} \sigma_{pr} = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

After some algebraic transformations the last expression is reduced to the form

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial c}{\partial \theta} & = -(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 \sin 2\psi \times \\
& \times \left[A_1 \frac{1+\eta}{1-\eta} + A_2 \cos 2\psi + \frac{A_3}{\sigma_1 - \sigma_2} \right] = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
A_1 & = s_{11} - s_{22}, \quad A_2 = s_{11} + s_{22} - 2s_{12} - s_{66}, \\
A_3 & = (\sigma_i^I - \sigma_i^{II}) s_{66}, \quad \eta = \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_1}.
\end{aligned}$$

From the second derivative of the goal function we have the following sufficient minimum condition

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial \theta^2} & = -2(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 \left(\cos 2\psi \left[A_1 \frac{1+\eta}{1-\eta} + \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. + A_2 \cos 2\psi + \frac{A_3}{\sigma_1 - \sigma_2} \right] - A_2 \sin^2 2\psi \right) > 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

For the case when $\sigma_1 \neq \sigma_2$, the roots of the equation (11) are: $\psi = 0^\circ$, $\psi = \pm 90^\circ$, $\psi = \pm \frac{1}{2} \arccos \tau$, where

$$\tau = -\frac{1}{A_2} \left[A_1 \frac{1+\eta}{1-\eta} + \frac{A_3}{\sigma_1 - \sigma_2} \right].$$

For $A_2 > 0$ from (12) we have

$$\cos 2\psi [\cos 2\psi - \tau] - \sin^2 2\psi < 0. \tag{13}$$

So $\psi = 0^\circ$ is the minimum if $\tau > 1$, $\psi = \pm 90^\circ$ is the minimum if $\tau < -1$. The inequality (13) is true for $\cos 2\psi = \tau$ so that $\psi = \pm \frac{1}{2} \arccos \tau$ is minimum for $|\tau| < 1$. For each τ there exist only one minimum, so it is the global minimum.

For $A_2 < 0$ from (12) we have

$$\cos 2\psi [\cos 2\psi - \tau] - \sin^2 2\psi > 0. \tag{14}$$

So $\psi = 0^\circ$ is the minimum if $\tau < 1$, $\psi = \pm 90^\circ$ is the minimum if $\tau > -1$. $\psi = \pm \frac{1}{2} \arccos \tau$ cannot be the minimum. From the analysis we can define the following rule for the global minimum:

If: $A_2 > 0$ and $|\tau| < 1$ the value $\psi^* = \pm \frac{1}{2} \arccos \tau$ is the global minimum;

else: one of the roots $\psi = 0^\circ$ or $\psi = \pm 90^\circ$ must be selected after comparing the minimum compliance functions:

$$\begin{aligned}
c_\psi & = \bar{\sigma}^T S \bar{\sigma} = \bar{\sigma}^T R^T (\gamma + \psi) S_H R(\gamma + \psi) \bar{\sigma} = \\
& = \bar{\sigma}_{pr}^T R^T(\psi) S_H R(\psi) \bar{\sigma}_{pr}.
\end{aligned}$$

From $c_0 - c_{90} = (\sigma_1^2 - \sigma_2^2) A_1$ we obtain:

if $(\sigma_1^2 - \sigma_2^2) A_1 < 0$, $\psi^* = 0^\circ$, else $\psi^* = 90^\circ$.

5 Sensitivity analysis (coupled problem)

In the case of coupled thermoelasticity problem, the equation of the load vector, $f = f_M + f_T$ is decomposed into the sum of the mechanical and thermal parts (here only f_T depends on θ). Now (6) can be reformulated:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial c_{obj}}{\partial \theta} &= 2 \frac{\partial (f_M + f_T)^T}{\partial \theta} u - u^T \frac{\partial K}{\partial \theta} u = \\
&= 2 \left[\frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \frac{\partial \Delta T}{\partial \theta} \right]^T u - u^T \frac{\partial K}{\partial \theta} u = \\
&= u_e^T \left[2 \int_e B^T \frac{\partial R^{-1}}{\partial \theta} \sigma_H de_e - \frac{\partial K_e}{\partial \theta} u_e \right] + \\
&+ 2u^T \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \frac{\partial \Delta T}{\partial \theta}.
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Considering that

$$\frac{\partial \Delta T}{\partial \theta} = \frac{\partial (T - T_0)}{\partial \theta} = \frac{\partial T}{\partial \theta} = -K_T^{-1} \frac{\partial K_T}{\partial \theta} T,$$

where T_0 is the constant reference temperature, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial c_{obj}}{\partial \theta} &= u_e^T \left\{ 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \Delta T - \frac{\partial K}{\partial \theta} u \right\}_e - \\
&- 2u^T \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} K_T^{-1} \frac{\partial K_T}{\partial \theta} T,
\end{aligned}$$

here brackets $\{\cdot\}_e$ mean that expression inside is calculated for an element e . The first term of the last relation is equal to (7) and introducing pseudo temperature vector $T_W^T = u^T \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} K_T^{-1}$, the second term can be written in the form

$$u^T \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} K_T^{-1} \frac{\partial K_T}{\partial \theta} T = T_W^T \frac{\partial K_T}{\partial \theta} T = \left\{ T_W^T \frac{\partial K_T}{\partial \theta} T \right\}_e,$$

where T_W is solution of the system of linear equations:

$$K_T T_W = \left[\frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \right]^T u. \tag{16}$$

The global conductivity matrix K_T is factorized during solving the heat transfer problem and $\frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T}$ is a matrix of derivatives with dimension $2n \times n$ (n is the count of nodes). The matrix for bilinear element can be calculated in the form:

$$\left[\frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \right]_{(i,j)} = \int_e [B^T R(-\theta) \beta]_i \varphi_j, \quad i=1, \dots, 8; \quad j=1, \dots, 4,$$

where φ_j is the basis function and B is the matrix of the basis function derivatives. Here $T = \sum_{i=1}^4 T_i \varphi_i$.

Note, that the goal function can be also presented as:

$$\begin{aligned}
c_{obj} &= u^T f = u^T f_M + u^T f_T = u^T f_M + \\
&+ u^T \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \Delta T = u^T f_M + T_W^T K_T \Delta T.
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

For pure thermal loading ($f_M = 0$):

$$c_{obj} = u^T K u = u^T \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \Delta T = T_W^T K_T \Delta T, \tag{18}$$

It can be seen that the goal of the optimization is the minimization of the ΔT (difference of the temperature) over the region with certain nodal weights, which are equal to strain multiplied by thermal stress and divided by the temperature. The sensitivity for (18) can be presented in the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial c_{obj}}{\partial \theta} &= \frac{\partial u^T}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \Delta T + u^T \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \Delta T + \\
&+ u^T \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \frac{\partial \Delta T}{\partial \theta} = \left\{ -2T_W^T \frac{\partial K_T}{\partial \theta} T + \right. \\
&\left. + 2u_e^T \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \Delta T - u^T \frac{\partial K}{\partial \theta} u \right\}_e.
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Now the algorithm for computation of the sensitivities can be constructed in the form:

1. Solving of the three systems of linear equations:

$$K_T T = F_T, \quad K u = f(T), \quad K_T T_W = \left[\frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T} \right]^T u;$$

For calculation of $T_W^T \frac{\partial K_T}{\partial \theta} \Delta T$ we have used the homogenous boundary condition for $\frac{\partial T}{\partial \theta}$ in the points with fixed temperature.

2. Calculation of the derivative over matrixes for each finite element:

$$\frac{\partial K_T}{\partial \theta}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial f_T}{\partial \Delta T}, \quad \frac{\partial K}{\partial \theta};$$

3. Calculation $\frac{\partial c_{obj}}{\partial \theta}$ for each element using (19).

For solving local optimization problem for an element, (19) is reformulated in stress terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
&- 2 \nabla T_W^T \frac{\partial [R_i^T(\theta) \mathbf{k}_i R_i(\theta)]}{\partial \theta} \nabla T + 2 \bar{\sigma}_H^T W S_H R(\theta) \bar{\sigma} + \\
&+ \bar{\sigma}^T \frac{\partial [R^T(\theta) S_H R(\theta)]}{\partial \theta} \bar{\sigma} = 0,
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

where $\mathbf{k}_t = \begin{bmatrix} k_1 & 0 \\ 0 & k_2 \end{bmatrix}$ and $R_t(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix}$

are conductivity and rotation matrices. In the following, all expressions are related to an element e , and the notation $\{\cdot\}_e$ is omitted for the simplicity.

Considering that $\bar{\sigma}_H^T WS_H = [0, 0, A_3]$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & a_1 \cos 2\theta + a_2 \sin 2\theta + \\ & + A_3 [(\bar{\sigma}_2 - \bar{\sigma}_1) \sin 2\theta + 2\bar{\sigma}_{12} \cos 2\theta] + \\ & + \bar{\sigma}^T \frac{\partial [R^T(\theta) S_H R(\theta)]}{\partial \theta} \bar{\sigma} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= -2(k_1 - k_2) [(\nabla T_W)_2 (\nabla T)_1 + (\nabla T_W)_1 (\nabla T)_2], \\ a_2 &= 2(k_1 - k_2) [(\nabla T_W)_1 (\nabla T)_1 - (\nabla T_W)_2 (\nabla T)_2]. \end{aligned}$$

In (21) the first two terms are contribution of the conductivity, the next one due to thermal expansion and the last one due to the stiffness. Using algebraic transformations (21) can be written in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} & P_0 + P_1 \cos 2\theta + P_2 \sin 2\theta + P_3 \sin^2 2\theta + \\ & + P_4 \sin 2\theta \cos 2\theta = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} P_0 &= 2\bar{\sigma}_{12} (\bar{\sigma}_1 - \bar{\sigma}_2) A_2, \\ P_1 &= a_1 + 2\bar{\sigma}_{12} (A_3 + A_1(\bar{\sigma}_1 + \bar{\sigma}_2)), \\ P_2 &= a_2 - (\bar{\sigma}_1 - \bar{\sigma}_2) (A_3 + A_1(\bar{\sigma}_1 + \bar{\sigma}_2)), \\ P_3 &= -4\bar{\sigma}_{12} (\bar{\sigma}_1 - \bar{\sigma}_2) A_2, \\ P_4 &= (4\bar{\sigma}_{12}^2 - (\bar{\sigma}_1 - \bar{\sigma}_2)^2) A_2. \end{aligned}$$

Note that for pure mechanical loading ($a_1 = a_2 = 0$ and $A_3 = 0$). The polynomial equation (22) is reduced to the corresponding stress-based equation [5]. For the constant temperature or isotropy of the conductivity ($a_1 = a_2 = 0$) in the equation (22), the contribution due to the thermal expansion can be presented as:

$$\begin{aligned} & A_3 [2\bar{\sigma}_{12} \cos 2\theta - (\bar{\sigma}_1 - \bar{\sigma}_2) \sin 2\theta] = \\ & = -A_3 (\sigma_1 - \sigma_2) \sin 2\psi, \end{aligned}$$

which is the thermal expansion term in equation (11).

Using

$$\sin 2\theta = \frac{2 \operatorname{tg} \theta}{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta}, \quad \cos 2\theta = \frac{1 - \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta}{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta}.$$

(22) can be rewritten in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} & P_0 + P_1 \frac{1 - \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta}{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta} + P_2 \frac{2 \operatorname{tg} \theta}{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta} + P_3 \frac{4 \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta}{(1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta)^2} + \\ & + P_4 \frac{2 \operatorname{tg} \theta (1 - \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta)}{(1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta)^2} = 0, \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} & P_0 (1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta)^2 + P_1 (1 - \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta) + 2P_2 \operatorname{tg} \theta (1 + \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta) + \\ & + 4P_3 \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta + 2P_4 \operatorname{tg} \theta (1 - \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta) = \\ & = (P_0 - P_1) \operatorname{tg}^4 \theta + 2(P_2 - P_4) \operatorname{tg}^3 \theta + \\ & + 2(P_0 + 2P_3) \operatorname{tg}^2 \theta + 2(P_2 + P_4) \operatorname{tg} \theta + P_0 + P_1 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

For $z = \operatorname{tg} \theta$, following equation is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} & (P_0 - P_1) z^4 + 2(P_2 - P_4) z^3 + 2(P_0 + 2P_3) z^2 + \\ & + 2(P_2 + P_4) z + P_0 + P_1 = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

From the numerical solution of the polynomial equation (23) we obtain four roots called z_i and corresponding values of $\theta_i = \operatorname{arctg} z_i$, $z_i \in \mathbb{R}$, $i = 1, \dots, 4$, which satisfy necessary optimality condition of local problem. Considering the possible minimum (refer [5]) for $\theta_5 = \frac{\pi}{2}$ too, the optimal orientation is selected by comparison of the element energy:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{loc}(\theta_i) &= \bar{\sigma}^T S(\theta_i) \bar{\sigma} + 2\varepsilon^T \sigma_t(\theta_i) - \\ & - 2\nabla T_W^T \mathbf{k}_t(\theta_i) \nabla T, \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

for $\theta_i = \operatorname{arctg} z_i$, $z_i \in \mathbb{R}$, $i = 1, \dots, 5$.

6 Numerical results

Numerical experiments were provided for two types of the thermo-elastic problems. FE model and optimization procedure were implemented using the self-written Matlab algorithms.

6.1. Thermoelastic problem ($\Delta T(\mathbf{x}) = \text{const}$).

Let the two-dimensional rectangular domain Ω be subjected to the mechanical load 10^7 N in the center

of the top line, with fixed left and right sides (see Fig. 3). The size of the specimen is 0.12 by 0.04 meters and the constant temperature differential is $\Delta T(\mathbf{x})=100, \forall \mathbf{x} \in \Omega$. The problem is modeled by FEM with 30×10 plane-stress finite elements. The Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio [1], coefficients of thermal expansion [12] and volume fraction of the ceramic and metal phases are:

$$E_c = 390 \text{ GPa}, \nu_c = 0.24, \alpha_c = 6.1 \times 10^{-6}, V_c = 0.4,$$

$$E_m = 80 \text{ GPa}, \nu_m = 0.33, \alpha_m = 19.8 \times 10^{-6}, V_m = 0.6.$$

The initial orientation of the domains is horizontal. The solution for temperature distribution and the optimal material orientation for different types of loading obtained by stress-based method is presented in the Fig. 4-6. The optimization procedure of strain-based method oscillates between two "optimal" configurations shown in the Fig. 7.

The compliance energy during the optimization process (5 iterations) obtained by stress- and strain-based methods is presented in Fig. 8.

6.2. Coupled thermoelastic problem.

This problem is almost identical to the previous one, however the temperature difference ΔT varies over the domain Ω and also depends on material orientation θ .

The thermal conductivities of Al_2O_3 and Al-12Si are $k_c = 33 \text{ W/m-K}$ [13] and $k_m = 136.8 \text{ W/m-K}$ [14]

correspondingly. The temperature $T = 0^\circ \text{C}$ and displacement $u = 0$ are applied to the left and right edges of the specimen, and the top side is loaded by the heat $F_T = 2 \times 31 \text{ kW}$ (2 kW is imposed in 31 FEM nodes). The reference temperature is $T_0 = 20^\circ \text{C}$ (see Fig. 9).

The element optimal orientation is found from (23). The iterative solution process was provided until the change of the element angle is less than 1 degree. Results of the optimization for different values of the mechanical load applied to central top node $F_M = 0, 1, 10 \text{ MN}$ are presented on the figures 10-12. Fig. 13 shows change of the energy (objective function) during iteration process. The convergence for all three iteration processes is monotonic.

7 Summary

The methodology for optimization of the local material orientation (orthotropic material) for thermoelasticity problem is proposed. The goal of the optimization is minimization of the compliance

energy. Two formulations are considered in these studies. In the first one, the thermal stresses are dependent on the material orientation and are independent in the second one. Local sensitivity analysis was performed in the terms of stresses. The numerical results demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed methods.

Fig. 1. Typical lamellar microstructure: dark grey is the ceramics and light grey is the metal.

Fig. 2. Coordinate system transformation.

Fig. 3. Initial design of the FE model: geometry, boundary conditions and initial (horizontal) lamella orientation in all elements.

Fig. 4. Microstructure optimization for thermo-mechanical loading using stress-based method: displacements and lamella orientation in a) initial and b) optimal microstructure.

Fig. 5. Microstructure optimization for thermal loading using stress-based method: displacements and lamella orientation in a) initial and b) optimal microstructure.

Fig. 6. Microstructure optimization for mechanical loading using stress-based method: displacements and lamella orientation in a) initial and b) optimal microstructure.

Fig. 7. Optimal configurations obtained by strain-based method: a) 4th and b) 5th iterations.

Fig. 8. Compliance energy (in J) of the specimen for different iteration steps obtained by using the strain- and stress-based methods.

Fig. 9. Initial design of the FE model (coupled problem): geometry, boundary conditions and initial (horizontal) lamella orientation in all elements.

Fig. 10. Microstructure optimization for thermal loading (38 iterations): displacements and lamella orientation in a) initial and b) optimal microstructure.

Fig. 11. Microstructure optimization for thermo-mechanical (1 MN) loading (10 iterations): displacements and lamella orientation in a) initial and b) optimal microstructure.

Fig. 12. Microstructure optimization for thermo-mechanical (10 MN) loading (10 iterations): displacements and lamella orientation in a) initial and b) optimal microstructure.

Fig. 13. Compliance energy (in J) of the specimen for different iteration steps for different loading cases.

Acknowledgements

Financial support of the DFG (PI785/1-2 and PI785/3-2) is gratefully acknowledged.

References

- [1] S. Roy "Metal/ceramic composites from freeze-cast preforms: domain structure and mechanical properties". Shaker, 2009.
- [2] P. Pedersen "On optimal orientation of orthotropic materials". *Struct. Optimization*, Vol. 1, pp 101–106, 1989.
- [3] M.P. Bendsoe, O. Sigmund "Topology optimization". Springer, 2003.
- [4] G. Cheng, P. Pedersen "On sufficiency conditions for optimal design based on extremum principles of mechanics". *J. Mech. Physics Solids*, Vol. 45, No. 1, pp 135–150, 1997. H.C. Gea, J.H. Luo "On the stress-based and strain-based methods for predicting optimal orientation of orthotropic materials". *Struct Multidisc Optim*, Vol. 26, pp 229–234, 2004.
- [5] R. Piat, Y. Sinchuk, M. Vasoya, O. Sigmund "Minimal compliance design for metal–ceramic

- composites with lamellar microstructures”. *Acta Materialia*, Vol. 59, pp 4835-4846, 2011.
- [6] H. Rodrigues, P. Fernandes “A material based model for topology optimization of thermoelastic structures”. *Int. J. Numer. Meth. Engng.*, Vol. 38, pp 1951-1965, 1995.
- [7] B. Desmorat “Structural rigidity optimization with an initial design dependent stress field. Application to thermo-elastic stress loads”. *European J. Mech. A Solids*, Vol. 37, pp 150-159, 2013.
- [8] R.A. Schapery “Thermal expansion coefficients of composite materials based on energy principles”. *J. Comp. Mater.*, Vol. 2, pp 380-404, 1968.
- [9] G.M. Gladysza, K.K. Chawlab, “Coefficients of thermal expansion of some laminated ceramic composites”. *Composites: Part A*, Vol. 32, pp 173–178, 2001.
- [10] K.Z. Markov “*Heterogeneous Media: Modeling and Simulation*”. Ed. K.Z. Markov, L. Preziosi, Birkhauser, Boston, 1999.
- [11] P. Albrecht “*Thermische Ausdehnung und Schädigung in Gefriergelassenen Metall-Keramik-Verbundwerkstoffen*”. Bachelorarbeit, Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, 2012.
- [12] R.G. Munro “Evaluated Material Properties for a Sintered α -Alumina”. *J. American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 80, pp 1919-1928, 1997.
- [13] C.P. Kothandaraman, S. Subramanyam “*Heat and mass transfer data book*”, 7th edition, New Age International Publishers, 2010.